

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIFFICULTIES IN RAISING CHILDREN AND TEENAGERS - IS THE INTERNET EVIL OR GOOD?

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Abstract

Family education is the most significant process in the life of any child. The presence of the older generation of grandparents in the family in the socialization of the new generation is an integral part of the educational process. But technology also plays an important role in the education of the younger generation.

The article examines some aspects of raising the younger generation under the influence of ICT and all sorts of gadgets. The most important question of our research today is the question of how long a child and teenager spend on social networks per day. And whether the Internet is evil or good will be shown by further research within the framework of family education.

Keywords: internet, gadgets, digital environment, education, new generation, family education

Parenting has always been a great challenge. But since the beginning of the 21st century, this has become the most important issue of modern pedagogy. If grandmothers' worries were often only of a domestic nature, today parents feel psychological pressure. Most importantly, parents look at the future with distrust. However, if we compare the lives of adults of different generations, it is noticeable that life is harder today, and it has become much more difficult to raise a good person.

Unlike in the past, when parents could confidently predict a child's future profession and life path, the modern world is full of uncertainty. The development and upbringing of children of old patterns no longer guarantee success. Parents have to adapt to new realities and raise a child who is able to learn quickly, adapt and master new skills. This leads to what is called "stealing childhood" from a child. Life requires new skills, not only from an adult, but also from a child. From the very first years of life, parents begin to drive their child to foreign language courses, online lessons, computer courses, etc. When should a child play, jump, run, or just be a child? Today, this is the most important issue in the upbringing of the younger generation.

The world of the future is frightening, and in the pursuit of a reliable parenting strategy, adults often turn to experts, but face individual, ambiguous recommendations. The lack of a single correct solution forces us to focus on the results of research, which often contradict each other.

Since 2010, Russia has proposed a strategy for raising children in schools. In Azerbaijan, since 2005, educating the younger generation within the framework of mentality, traditions, multiculturalism and integration outside the country has occupied a special place in state policy, taking into account the severity of innovations and information technology development around the world.

A reliable parenting strategy involves the consistent application of various methods and approaches aimed at shaping the child's personality, moral qualities, skills and knowledge [1, v.102].

Nowadays, the process of raising children is about achieving big goals that even an adult cannot achieve. Modern parents are concerned not only about health, education and decency, but also about emotional well-being, the ability to communicate and make informed decisions. And here it is important that the child does not "lag behind" the neighbor's child. As a result, the child puts the entire burden of decisions on the parents, or the parents themselves take all the responsibility on their shoulders, protecting the child from social education. The popular practice of raising children without restrictions gives unlimited freedom to tyrant children over slave parents. Children enjoy complete freedom while their parents assume full responsibility! [3. V.17].

In the conditions of family isolation, typical of modern society in large cities, parents are often deprived of informal help, which used to be provided by relatives (mainly grandparents) and neighbors. That's not all, every child sees grandparents through the eyes of their parents, and this is a serious obstacle to developing their own opinion of them [8. V.62].

Or, attacks by parents on grandparents that their methods are outdated and now they do worse than help with their advice. Each of the grandparents has their own style of upbringing. But at the same time, the styles of grandparental upbringing differ from the styles of parental upbringing. The styles of grandparental upbringing are related to the types of grandmothers identified above - "ordinary", "passionate" and "distant". The contribution of grandparents to family life depends on the personal characteristics of the older person and social conditions [5. V.288]. Psychologists partially compensate for this lost support, but cannot replace full communication and family upbringing of children.

In the 90s, younger students aged 7-12, when they entered school, found themselves in a situation of evaluation and learning something new for the first time. The teacher was the only authority and keeper of knowledge that the child could touch. "...The study of the preschool period of childhood has made it possible

to establish serious changes in children's attitudes towards themselves, towards adults and peers, and towards objective reality" [6, v.298].

Nowadays, the authority of the teacher and school grades has fallen significantly due to the fact that many alternative options for gaining knowledge about the world have appeared: children's educational applications, online courses, videos on platforms. Thus, "...a teacher who tries to teach children to think and establish cause-and-effect relationships through exercises and repetition requires much more effort from them than watching ready-made content without further reinforcement, without homework" [7, v. 5-19].

In her work "On the Child's Side," the French psychologist Dolto wrote: "Sometimes it can be very difficult to reach a child, to overcome his resistance and the parental "I want it this way, it's my right, because I'm an adult" [2, v. 722]. In early adolescence, the leading activity is interpersonal communication, when children learn to make friends, recognize emotions, build relationships, and learn their boundaries. They learn to cooperate and self-identify in a significant group. Certain interpersonal relationships form different family characters, as suggested by Dreikurs R. and Zoltz (2011).

In the 2000s, social networks began to appear, where communication and behavior moved online. Modern children are more inclined to safety and distance, since setting their boundaries, committing "bad" deeds and learning about the feelings of those who exhibit auto-aggressive behavior or external aggression can be done via the Internet. On the one hand, nowadays children often prefer to stay at home rather than go for a walk in dangerous places, and on the other hand, being within four walls cannot be considered a life, social experience. The psyche does not perceive watching videos with someone else's physical and emotional experience as an emotional and personal experience for itself. In this regard, modern teenagers are less competent, have less developed communication skills and weak emotional intelligence. They are not always able to correctly decipher their emotions, which in late adolescence from 14 to 17 years old leads to the problem of self-determination. This is where the modern young family begins, which wants to solve its problems "online". What will the online solution, online education, online greeting, online virtual love, etc. lead to? At this period of education, these issues multiply their relevance.

The digital environment is attractive due to its openness, accessibility, and the absence of a permanent system of norms and rules, as it allows one to adapt to trends, change one's position and interests. This is especially important for teenagers, because they are in a situation of identity formation. They want to choose, but real life, unlike digital life, does not always provide such an opportunity. Reality frightens them, and pressure from relatives aggravates dependence on ICT.

The digital environment is anonymity, an illusion, when actions on the network are performed not by the child, but by his avatar. The child is "safe" and can at any time refuse his words, delete a post or account, commit some act for which he will not have to answer.

And most importantly, the digital environment is the absence of boundaries. In the digital environment,

social subordination, age and other boundaries, norms of behavior are erased (both adults and children play online games). Equality, often absent in real life, but present in the digital one, is especially attractive to teenagers.

Modern young parents give their children gadgets even at a young age, thereby opening the way for the child to express himself in accordance with the actions of his "heroes" seen. But when a gadget or digital environment is provided to a child, it should be a joint activity with an adult. It is important that the child learns to use the digital environment to achieve some goal, for playing or learning. For example, a child has a toy, and in the digital environment you can bring this toy to life and understand what properties it has. Staying in the gadget should be controlled so that the child receives additional knowledge about objects and phenomena of real life.

According to the data of the Faculty of Psychology of the Lomonosov Moscow State University, studies were conducted on a sample of more than a thousand children from all over the country (preschoolers and primary school students). The children were studied for their cognitive and emotional spheres according to the time spent in the digital environment. Based on this study, the following recommendations were formed. For preschool and primary school age, the optimal time spent on the Internet is 30 minutes a day (with breaks). Children who spend more than an hour a day on gadgets have problems with emotional intelligence and are worse at recognizing and managing emotions.

In early and late adolescence, gadget use should be limited to no more than an hour or two a day [4, v.290]. When in a digital environment for a long time, teenagers do not engage their thinking and attention, and do not analyze information. The child may experience disappointment and dissatisfaction with real life and seek to replace their unresolved problems with virtual achievements. They may be unprepared for the efforts required in real life and lose interest in life.

We should not instill in children the belief that a gadget is something harmful. The more we prohibit or encourage gadgets, the more the child will strive to get into the digital world. My grandson is 2 years old, he does not eat unless he watches cartoons on his phone. This is very bad - he does not feel hungry, does not know if he wants to eat. But, although he is 2 years old, he knows the English alphabet very well, knows and distinguishes colors in English, can name more than 15 letters in English. This is the positive side of gadgets. Another positive quality of the digital environment is that children have the opportunity to interact with the world.

With the correct use of the Internet, a teenager can improve their communication skills by communicating with people at a distance, learn languages with native speakers, and learn about the cultures of the world. All this has a positive effect on the harmonious development of the child's personality, creating opportunities for professional orientation and self-determination.

With such an abundance of educational tools, parents are at a loss in their choice. There is no universal recipe for raising successful and happy people. Parents choose different strategies, focusing on the problems of

raising children - emotional closeness, education, life skills development or environmental well-being. More opportunities have appeared, but less energy and time. If you have free time, spend it with your child: no gadgets, expensive phones or toys can replace hugs, kisses and smiles of their parents. Walks in the fresh air and games of tag are the best means for relationships and expressions of love, and children who have grown up in love and harmony in society are more needed than future robot workers.

The advent of wireless internet and the ability to work remotely create the illusion of comprehensive access to tasks and spoil modern child rearing. Parents have to combine it with professional responsibilities, which can even lead to burnout. Children do not owe anything to anyone, you cannot force them onto a conveyor belt of endless work. Children exist because YOU wanted them. You must devote your precious time and resources to their upbringing and a good life. You cannot forever say that you gave up something for the sake of the child, he did not ask you.

Modern parents study scientific literature, attend seminars and try to keep up with the latest trends so that the birth and upbringing of children goes as well as possible [9].

The choice of priorities and work-life balance are born in the analysis of life activity, when at any moment you can be seized by panic anxiety: what if I do the wrong thing or cause psychological trauma to the child?

We often "travel" through social networks unsystematically, aimlessly. The sense of time is lost on the Internet and we spend more time than we plan. Even when communicating with people, we want to check social networks from time to time. Sometimes destructive behavior can develop (forgetting to have lunch, not getting enough sleep because we were "hanging out" on the Internet). Of course, this is not a complete list of symptoms, not all of them necessarily manifest in one person. But if you have noticed at least half of it and you understand that it is interfering with your life, it is worth thinking about. We are all overloaded with information, which is associated with the emergence of the FOMO syndrome - the fear of missing out on opportunities everywhere. The FOMO effect (fear of missing out) is a syndrome of missed benefits [10]. It usually manifests itself as anxiety about the fact that something important, exciting or useful is happening somewhere right now, and you do not know about it and can miss it. A number of scientists believe that the danger of the FOMO syndrome is exaggerated. For example, Ivan Lebedev, a specialist in the psychological service of the RANEP Institute of Social Sciences, claims: "If this is a habit – and anxiety arises from the fact that I have not read the news for two days, perhaps something happened in the world, and I do not know about it, then this is normal. Technologies have entered our lives firmly and are not going to leave. And any escalation in the

spirit of "the Internet is evil" or "FOMO is the new plague of the 21st century" should be divided by seven. Scrolling through social networks does not pose any mortal danger in itself, it is only a consequence of technological progress, scrolling the feed is a kind of time killer" [11].

Conclusions. What conclusions can be drawn? Is the Internet evil? Is the Internet a resource for education? It is impossible to come to a unanimous decision on issues of either the Internet or education. A conscious person always has a choice. We are not obliged to conform to the cults of productivity and successful success. We just need to love the child, show interest in his inclinations. Show that you care about his opinion. And most importantly, listen to your child. After all, they do not have to be perfect every day.

A parent with weaknesses, who tries, makes mistakes and shares difficult experiences, is much better than a successful businessman.

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